

STEM IN THE FUTURE: TRANSFORMING EDUCATION FOR SUSTAINABILITY

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Abstract

The European Green Deal states that schools play an important role in engaging with students and the wider community for environmental sustainability and develop the skills needed for a successful transition to a sustainable society. To explore the role of STEM education in sustainability, Scientix, the community for science education in Europe, organised an online Science Topics Networking Seminar (STNS) in collaboration with the projects GreenSCENT and Life Terra. At the event, more than 20 experts representing various stakeholders in STEM education came together to discuss good practices in STEM education in promoting sustainability education and supporting a green future. This observatory paper outlines the key discussion points raised during the seminar, supported by research from the scientific literature. First, there is an abundance of STEM resources and teaching material. There is a need to facilitate the evaluation and exchange of these resources and provide time and support to teachers for implementing them in their classrooms. Second, students could be more involved in sustainability activities that will help them see their impact on their immediate surrounding. This can be achieved with interdisciplinary activities that combine scientific concepts, critical thinking and active citizenship. A whole-school approach and greenifying schools can further engage students in taking action and be more motivated for STEM projects for sustainability. Third, more activities need to adopt the GreenComp and perform

assessments based on it to test it as a competence framework. Finally, STEM education for sustainability can be further supported with school visits to nature reserves, science centres and companies involved in sustainability.

Keywords: Education for sustainable development, eco-school, environmental education, sustainability, sustainability competences, GreenComp

Introduction

Although nations responded well to many global problems in the past and showed their capacity to work together, the world needs to further raise its ability to adapt and learn what works in the face of complex topics such as fast digitalisation, climate change, inequality, food waste and sustainable energy. STEM education for the environment and sustainability is crucial because the students of today are the scientists, decision-makers, teachers and parents of the future, who will approach societal needs with the sustainability of the world in mind and will guarantee that the next generation will also adopt the skills and attitudes needed for the future (Carbonell-Alcocer et al., 2022).

In 2019, the European Commission issued the European Green Deal¹ with the goal of becoming climate-neutral by 2050. The European Green Deal emphasises that schools play an important role in engaging with pupils and the wider community for environmental sustainability and develop the skills needed for a successful transition to a sustainable society. School education is crucial for a positive impact on the environment and innovation towards sustainability. It also helps reconnecting individuals with the environment and their community, promoting their health and well-being. GreenComp (Bianchi et al., 2022), the new European sustainability competence framework published by the Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the European Commission, maps out the competences needed for the green transition and provides a shared competence framework on sustainability at European level as a common basis to guide both educators and learners. Also, the renewed Digital Education Action Plan (2021-27) EU policy initiative emphasises that digital skills should include the knowledge of the impact of digital technologies on the environment and sustainability of the world (EC, 2020).

Equipping students with knowledge about sustainability is hardly enough to translate to action. It requires pupils to reflect on their attitudes and be aware of the societal and environmental changes that impact their immediate surroundings. STEM education should also promote a

¹ EUR-Lex - 52019DC0640 - EN - EUR-Lex (europa.eu)
<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1576150542719&uri=COM%3A2019%3A640%3AFIN>

sense of connection for pupils through a community that shares the same values about the environment and other local issues. It should also combine scientific knowledge, critical thinking and active citizenship, connecting STEM education with the arts, humanities and social sciences.

This STNS entitled ‘STEM in the Future: What is the role of schools in the Green Transition?’ explored the challenges and good practices in STEM education tackling sustainability in schools. The seminar provided an opportunity to discuss the impact of STEM education, eco-schools², and other projects and initiatives on sustainability-related competences and behaviours of students. The seminar brought together a diverse group of stakeholders to exchange knowledge and to set the grounds for new partnerships and collaborations. Attendees included representatives from Ministries of Education (MoEs) and the industry, teachers, policymakers, researchers, teacher trainers and education consultants.

This paper offers the main outcomes from this STNS held online on 1 June 2022. It combines a literature review based on the research and projects mentioned by the attendees during the discussions in the seminar, as well as their observations in their personal and professional lives related to environmental education and education for sustainable development. Therefore, by combining theory, research and practice, the paper offers a unique account of the European landscape of STEM-related initiatives, projects, and interventions to fostering sustainability competences in students.

From environmental education to education for sustainable development

There are two main trends in teaching about ecology and sustainability: (1) environmental education (EE); and (2) education for sustainable development (ESD) (Castellanos & Queiruga-Dios, 2022). EE is a trend that emerged earlier and has been around for decades. EE aims to activate citizens to act in their community, through providing them knowledge, values and experiences with the local surroundings (Ardoin et al., 2020). In this way, many schools set out with the mission to prepare the young generations through project-based learning and community service to safeguard the environment and become the environmental leaders and innovators of the future.

Environmental education has evolved into education for sustainable development (ESD), spearheaded by United Nations’ adoption of this term through the Decade of ESD³. ESD

² <https://www.ecoschools.global/>

³ [UN Decade of ESD \(unesco.org\)](https://www.unesco.org/en/decade-of-education-for-sustainable-development)

emphasises that there is a need for an approach that considers societal and economic implications (e.g., Uitto et al., 2017) of environmental issues. ESD is also matched to the sustainable development goals (SDGs)⁴ set by UNESCO (2017). ESD can also be considered a more human-centred approach compared to EE, because it also includes education about inclusion, equity, human rights and democracy (Wals, 2012).

Environmental education in schools

Green schools⁵, eco-schools⁶ and environmental schools started emerging all over Europe and the world at the end of the 20th century, often supported by the Ministries of Education. In the country reports of the eco-schools' movement, it appears that professional development opportunities for EE are offered in virtually all central and north European countries (FEE, 2019a) often organised by public authorities and higher education institutions, and sometimes by NGO's. Conversely EE in the eastern European countries seems to be the remit of science teachers, and where continuous professional development is organised, it is mostly by universities or NGO's. The latter also seems to be the case in southern European countries (FEE, 2019b).

Some recent examples are the ECOLOG programme in Austria (Rauch & Pfaffenwimmer, 2014, 2020), the MOS (Environmental Education at School) programme in Flanders (Boeve-de Pauw & Van Petegem, 2019), the eco-schools programmes in Turkey (Taşar, 2020) and Sweden (Gericke et al., 2020), natural/eco-schools in Finland (Uitto et al. 2017) and Scotland (Pirrie et al. 2006), and many others described in the book *Green Schools Globally* (Gough et al., 2020).

Eco-schools typically adopt a whole-school approach to set a model for sustainability for the community surrounding them (Andreou, 2020). This approach establishes a supportive learning environment where the institution is active on sustainability not only concerning teaching, but also planning and governance, active learning, staff participation, and the management of buildings and resources. The whole-school approach suggests that a green school or eco-school should develop a programme for professional development for the school staff and involve both staff and pupils in developing sustainable and green solutions for the

⁴ In 2015 the United Nations set up the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), a collection of interlinked 17 goals to be achieved by the year 2030 and designed to be a "blueprint to achieve a better and more sustainable future for all" - <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>

⁵ <https://projectgreenschools.org/>

school's energy and water consumption, waste management, transport, logistics and personal health.

Some examples of how sustainability/environmental education is addressed in schools:

- In Cyprus, environmental education is defined as a cross-disciplinary subject in the curriculum for pre-primary and primary levels. EE has allocated school time. 6 to 9 year-old students are taught environmental education for 80 minutes per week for half a school year, while 10 to 11 year-old students are taught for 40 minutes every week for the entire school year. Schools are also developing their own education policy for ESD. The Unit of Education for the Environment and Sustainable Development (EESD Unit) of the Ministry of Education, Culture, Youth and Sports was established officially in 2018 with the aim of implementing the National Strategy on EESD, which was realised in the 2000s. The EESD Unit implements a series of central actions:
 - The implementation and supervision of the National Network of Environmental Education Centres which offers opportunities for informal and non-formal education related to EESD issues to all levels of education and to lifelong learners.
 - Continuous Professional Development (CPD) of teachers which is mandatory and includes a variety of EESD topics at least as optional choices.
 - The development of educational material related to EESD.
 - The implementation of the national curriculum for EESD which was developed in 2009 with the main purpose of transforming schools into sustainable schools.

In pre-primary and primary education, the EESD curriculum is implemented through the schools' Sustainable Environmental Education Policy (SEEP) and in secondary education through the Action Plan for the Improvement of the School Unit (APISU). The SEEP/APISU is developed by the whole institution, and consequently the entire school community works towards its implementation. The issues included in the SEEP are agreed by the whole institution, and everyone in the school engages in their exploration and studies through the EESD curriculum's thematic units, both during the ESD subject (one hour per week) and during all other subjects. The SEEP requires cooperation with the community and with organisations and institutions. Schools perform a self-evaluation of SEEP to help them identify their progress regarding their transformation towards sustainability. This self-evaluation allows each school to decide whether to continue with the same ESD issues for the next school year, or to set a new issue.

- In Czechia, continuous professional development courses are offered to all teachers, and one teacher is appointed Environmental Education Coordinator in each school. This teacher must follow a specially designed course with a length of 250 hours and pass an exam to be entitled to this task.
- In Finland, since 2014 the national core curriculum defines that education for sustainable development should be taught with a holistic view and as a cross-curricular topic (Uitto & Saloranta, 2017). The curriculum also emphasises that the school should be a learning community that takes responsibility for the environment and focuses on a sustainable future. Finland has been organising nature visits for pupils since the 1950s and setting up Nature/Environmental Schools since 1986 (Jeronen et al., 2009). Such schools, like any school in Finland, are funded by the municipality.
- In Italy, since 2020, education for sustainable development has been integrated into the Italian Civics Education curriculum, to implement the law No 92 of 20 August 2019 passed by the Parliament. Environmental themes have been introduced as part of the compulsory Civic Education discipline in the curriculum of primary, secondary education and adult education (with an introduction in Early Childhood Education and Care). Students learn about 'environmental education, knowledge and protection of heritage and the territory'. The national Strategic Plan for Global Citizenship education situates education for sustainable development within global citizenship education.
- In Romania, pupils receive EE in extra-curricular activities mostly. The topic is also addressed in civic education lessons, which are optional in the curriculum. Romania started to improve education and awareness-raising on climate change mitigation and adaptation by means of occupational training, national ecological and environmental contests, and information and media campaigns to inform the general public and special campaigns for target groups. The MoE recently asked every school to organise a 'Green Week' and discussions have started to integrate nature-based solutions and environmental education further in the school curriculum⁷.
- In Poland, every school year the Ministry of Education announces priorities of the state educational policy. During last year (2021/2022), one of the priorities was dedicated to the implementation of environmental education at school. Scientix National Contact Point has also been providing support to Polish teachers by organising 'Green Tuesdays with Scientix' webinars. The webinars were dedicated to the most current

⁷ <https://www.usnews.com/news/world/articles/2022-01-11/romania-pushes-to-add-climate-change-education-in-schools>

environmental challenges and foreseen as a substantive help for in-service teachers interested in updating their knowledge in the field of climate change, renewable energy sources, plastic pollution, and water management issues.

- In many schools in Spain, the topic is often addressed by life sciences or natural sciences teachers. It is difficult to find teachers of other subjects who lead initiatives about sustainability in the classroom. Therefore, the implementation of environmental education in schools depends on the will of the management team to adopt sustainable development as one of the main lines of action, and of the teachers who teach subjects directly related to the environment. Biology teachers can provide environmental education by addressing current real-world problems such as climate change, microplastics, the poor management of waste, the energy crisis or the loss of biodiversity.
- In Sweden, sustainable development is not a separate subject, but the curriculum defines it as a topic to be addressed by all teachers. Eco-schools in Sweden have to meet certain criteria to obtain a certification, a process monitored by the non-governmental organisation Keep Sweden Tidy (Boeve-De Pauw et al., 2015).

Sustainability competences

An expert group has developed the European sustainability competence framework, named GreenComp, for the European Commission to promote learning on environmental sustainability in the European Union. The expert group included approximately 75 experts on sustainability education from academia and research institutions, youth representatives, educators and policy representatives from EU member states and NGOs. The framework identifies a set of 12 competences in four areas: (1) embodying sustainability values; (2) embracing complexity in sustainability; (3) envisioning sustainable futures; (4) acting for sustainability. GreenComp adopted sustainability in place of environmental sustainability to emphasise the multi-faceted quality of this issue (environmental, social, cultural and economic). According to the framework, sustainability means 'prioritising the needs of all life forms and of the planet by ensuring that human activity does not exceed planetary boundaries' (Bianchi, Pisiotis & Cabrera Giraldez, 2022, p. 12). The competences define what is needed to perform jobs related to sustainability, as well as all other jobs in a sustainable manner.

The framework provides a common ground for education stakeholders. Educators are encouraged to refer to this framework when developing their learning and training material to promote a shared understanding. The shared understanding of sustainability competences

can support education and training institutions to develop comparable practices and facilitate the sharing of knowledge and expertise.

This being said, GreenComp is a recent framework that still needs to be tested by practitioners. There is also a need to connect elements of this umbrella framework to specific content knowledge and subfields of sustainability. These open ends make it even more important for education and training institutions to align their vision of sustainability education with the framework.

For instance, the GREENSCENT⁸ H2020 project aims to support Green Deal policy implementation involving EU citizens, and especially youth, in co-creating material and in testing and validating GreenComp. The overarching goals of the project are: 1) to ensure that digital competences are part of GreenComp by demonstrating the link between the Green and the Digital transition; 2) to demonstrate the value of GreenComp by piloting a set of digital and analogue activities in real scenarios; and finally, 3) to facilitate the adoption of GreenComp by co-creating with experts, teachers and students.

Challenges

Lack of time and motivation

Project-based learning is one of the ideal methods to adopt for ESD, and interdisciplinary STEM topics can make great sustainability projects. However, preparing project-based work takes a lot of time for teachers. Teachers also need to follow the curriculum content and might find it difficult to address the topic within that curriculum content (Borg et al., 2012). Similarly, pupils need time to engage with the content and go through the stages of project-based learning. Although there are good resources, teachers also need time to search and find the resources that fit their needs. There is an abundance of resources but limited time in the curriculum to implement them.

Furthermore, even if a national goal is set for sustainability, environmental education cannot move forward if teachers and school leaders do not believe in its relevance. Interviews with pre-service teachers suggest that teachers can be more motivated if they experience outdoor activities and sustainability actions during their education (Kennely, Taylor & Maxwell, 2008).

⁸ <https://www.green-scent.eu/>

The adolescent dip

Around the age of 14-16, the interest in the environment seems to drop in favour of more developed urban areas, a phenomenon that has been called a “time out” (Kaplan & Kaplan, 2002). Also called “the adolescent dip”, this drop in interest seem to bounce back during young adulthood (Olsson et al., 2016). This has been observed in studies in Finland (Uitto et al., 2011), Germany (Liefländer & Bogner, 2014), Sweden (Olsson et al., 2016), Israel (Negev et al., 2008) and elsewhere. However, the adolescent dip seems to be independent of culture because it was also observed in studies in Asia (e.g., Olsson et al., 2019).

There is evidence that the dip is deeper in schools with an ESD certification (Olsson et al., 2016). Olsson and colleagues argue that this negative impact is due to ESD still being taught in a normative, teacher-centred way, aiming to ‘transfuse attitudes and behaviours to students’ (p.52). Indeed, for example, a stratified survey in Sweden showed that science teachers taught the subject of sustainability mostly in a fact-based tradition while social science teachers used more methods (e.g., group discussions, class debates and interdisciplinary work) than science teachers except that science teachers organised excursions more often than other teachers.

A society of the immediate

It can be argued that more than ever before, we live in a society of the immediate: ‘what I want I have to get now’. A preference for immediate results is not just a societal characteristic but also a biological one: humans and even other organisms tend to prefer smaller but immediate gains over larger but later gains. The later a benefit comes, the more the likelihood that this benefit can be lost due to unpredictable causes; therefore, this tendency to discount the future can be adaptive. However, in solving complex problems such as environmental sustainability, this tendency becomes maladaptive. Research shows that the magnitude of discounting the future is even higher in children and adolescents compared to adults (Daly & Wilson, 2005).

Future discounting could be one reason for the difficulty of students to see the benefits of taking action on the environment. When working with environmental issues, teachers need to show that they depend on natural processes that last for years, decades and even centuries. Often, people need a long time to see the consequences of their actions on the environment, while pupils have a different perception of time than adults (Michel, Harb & Hidalgo, 2012).

Teachers can explain in their classes that although the future is uncertain and investing in the future has higher risks, taking responsibility for the future is a question of human rights (Caney, 2009), because, for instance, in a future environmental crisis some people will be affected more negatively than others.

Means of explaining changes to the environment over a longer-term, such as simulations (e.g., Lee, et al., 2013), role playing activities (e.g. Karpudewan, Roth & Chandrasekhan, 2015) and online labs, can help pupils conceive change that takes place at a pace that exceeds the lifespan of humans. Open discussions that bring together people from different backgrounds was also an effective method to at least engage adults in the topic and to understand long-term effects of climate change (McNeal et al., 2014).

The other challenge is to instil respect and care for the environment. It is necessary to make students aware of their natural environment, for them to recognise how complex but also how fragile it is, and to become aware of their capability of loving and respecting it. Because one loves what one knows, not what is strange or unknown.

Way forward to improve education for sustainable development

Starting from early age

Research, quoted in the European Commission working document (2022), indicates that the early years are a crucial time window to develop a sustainability mindset and the concept of being an active citizen (Davis, 2015). Therefore, education for sustainable development should start well before children start primary school (Siraj-Blatchford et al., 2010). Indeed, a systematic review of existing research indicates that environmental education in early childhood education and care (ECEC) helps children's social and emotional development, and environmental education in ECEC needs to be in a natural setting and based on play and movement (Ardoin & Bowers, 2020).

Despite the potential impact of interventions for early childhood, the research literature, and initiatives for ESD in ECEC, is sparse (Davis, 2009). Nevertheless, there has been a small increase in initiatives over the last two decades (Ardoin & Bowers, 2020). There is also a need for training ECEC practitioners to support their capacity to address sustainability in their practice (Furu & Heilala, 2020).

It is clear that ESD must start from ECEC and continue throughout all education levels and forms. Primary school students in particular benefit from the sense that they are 'making a difference', whereas there is a deep interest in sustainability consciousness around adolescence. Special attention should be given to Vocational Education and Training (VET) as an enabler for the development of competences and skills for the green transition.

Inquiry-based and project-based learning

Research suggests that more activities could be used by teachers in STEM classes to address ESD (Borg et al., 2012). Inquiry-based activities were effective for teaching climate change (Porter, Weaver & Raptis, 2012; McNeal et al., 2014). Small group discussions also seem to be an effective way of teaching about the environment and can even be organised in the context of biology classes (Theobald et al., 2015).

Teachers can carry out interdisciplinary projects that involve several subjects so that students understand the environment in an integral way, not only for its natural aspects, but also for its social, economic, moral and cultural aspects. For instance, teachers can co-develop a project about plants in a specific landscape. The main objective of this work could be to compare the photosynthetic performance of different species of garden plants, to determine which of them was more efficient in absorbing carbon dioxide (CO₂) and whether this species was the one used in parks and gardens to make a better contribution to mitigate climate change. Students can measure the photosynthetic performance using ecological formulas and sensors programmed with Arduino⁹. Such real application projects where they contribute to society can get students engaged.

Another example could be a project in which students can design a mobile application that generates a notification when the user is in an area that will be flooded by the sea in the year 2100. By clicking on said notification, the application can direct the user to a web page created by the project with information on climate change (what it is, its causes, consequences, what to do, etc.).

Meeting scientists

Students' engagement and interest can be even higher if during their project they get to meet a scientist. This can also be successfully combined with a laboratory visit (Faria et al., 2015; Hallar, McCubbi & Wright, 2011).

Science experts and educators can collaborate to produce classroom teaching activities. For instance, Gold et al. (2015) showed a successful collaboration where researchers provided the scientific expertise, guidance in using tools such as Excel and Google Earth and data to analyse the albedo (i.e., whiteness level) of snow in the Arctic. Curriculum developers translated the material into learning modules that were tested by teachers in the classroom. The activities were well received by pupils, particularly because they could participate in the

⁹ Arduino is an open-source single-board microcontroller kit for building digital devices.
<https://www.arduino.cc/>

analysis of real-world data and understand the impact of snow on the environment (Gold et al., 2015).

Another example of a project that connects teachers, students and their families to science centres is the Remix The School project run by the Fab Lab in Barcelona¹⁰ with 10 schools, which aims to train teachers, students, and families to learn maker skills to develop solutions for local problems of food waste, biomaterials and sustainability. A unique aspect of the project is that it combines crafting and artisan techniques with digital manufacturing to produce materials such as soap, bioplastic and paper from food waste.

A whole-school approach to sustainability

In its European Commission staff working document, the Commission also pointed out that 'Schools, universities and other education and training institutions will become places where sustainability is not only taught, but also actively practised.' (European Commission, SWD, 2022, p. 8). It is obvious that only this way can education and training for environmental sustainability make all learning more relevant. It can also motivate students and educators alike to show greater societal engagement and thus develop competences for sustainability.

ESD requires supportive learning environments where the institution is active not only through teaching, but also planning and governance, active learning, staff participation, and the management of buildings and resources. Given the importance of how learning environments significantly impact pedagogical practice and student learning, there is an urgent need to adapt physical sites of learning for the green transition. Natural elements such as a play forest, trees, a lawn, a vegetable garden, a pond, etc. contribute to students' environmental affective behaviour because learning in nature creates a stronger ecological behaviour than just learning about it. Studies found that environmental education in a natural setting (e.g., a forest school or a conservation centre) leads to more ecological behaviour, especially in children with a sense of connectedness to nature (Otto & Pensini, 2017; Roczen et al., 2014).

Furthermore, the growing possibilities of using technology outdoors (e.g., mobile phones, tablets and augmented reality) could enhance this learning experience (Livingston, 2022). The certification as a 'green school', by combining pedagogical approaches to ESD, a whole school policy, and the presence and use of natural green elements, are key factors to successfully involve students' participation and care towards nature.

¹⁰ Fab Lab Barcelona is part of the Institute for Advanced Architecture of Catalonia. Fab Lab Barcelona aims to provide access to the tools, knowledge and means to educate, innovate and invent using technology and digital fabrication to allow anyone to make solutions to improve global and local lives and livelihoods. <https://fablabbcn.org/about>

In line with the 'green school' and whole-school approach, GREENSCENT and Schools Go Green¹¹ projects mobilise schools in Europe to pilot innovative digital tools and educational toolkits. Thus, student will experience real-life citizen science projects using: 1) the SCENT app and Cleanair@schools to increase air quality towards smart mobility and the potential use of nature-based solutions, and 2) the SCENT citizen journalism, powered interactive documentaries and augmented reality applications to contribute to environmental monitoring and awareness raising campaigns for local communities.

Hence, treating sustainability as a whole-school priority can help to create collaborations with parents, local businesses and others in the community. Often, the local reality of each school is different, and global sustainability education should be connected to actions for the local community to translate learning into active citizenship and action. Adolescents may be motivated to run crowd-sourcing campaigns for solutions in the local community.

Many schools can look for support to solve their waste management issues. Students are also not aware of the importance of reducing waste and composting (Kolbe, 2015) and rather focus on recycling. In fact, recycling might even work against the idea of reducing waste.

Students can be more in touch with nature and sustainability by doing urban gardening in their school. Planting, maintaining, and harvesting fruits and vegetables can help students understand the effort put into this task and value food waste reduction.

However, a study in Finland (Uitto et al., 2015) suggests that it is not enough to offer pupils ecological experiences at school (e.g., studying a product's life cycle, measuring water quality and calculating a personal ecological footprint). Students are more likely to engage in ecological actions outside of school if ecological experiences are combined with general pro-social experiences (e.g., school discussions related to welfare/bullying, visits to cultural institutions and joining aid campaigns) and actions that involve them in decision-making (e.g. enquiry to enhance school functions such as the school canteen, student organisation activities, international visits or student exchanges). A study in Sweden found that pupils are more likely to engage in sustainability behaviour if ESD is pluralistic, in the sense that it addresses multiple viewpoints in the topic (Boeve-De Pauw et al., 2015).

Finally, it is important that schools can take their actions beyond obtaining labels such as 'eco-school'. Too often the aim of green schools or eco-schools is to gain an award or a flag and instead the focus should be on self-directed learning (Pirrie et al., 2006).

¹¹ The Schools Go Green project, based on a Green Oriented Framework for primary schools, will pilot an educational toolkit linked to EU Green Deal topics, to evaluate pupils' acquisition of knowledge, skills and competences, based on the Open-Badges methodology. <https://schoolsgogreen.eu/>

Showcasing sustainability

Zero-waste houses and science centres are good ways both for piloting sustainability solutions and providing an inspirational model for pupils and teachers. For example:

- The National Science & Innovation Centre in the city of Kaunas¹² (also known as ‘Science Island’) in Lithuania is a project that was granted more than 20 million EUR by the European structural fund and the Lithuanian government to be set up as a science centre that consists of a permanent and temporary exhibition space, a virtual projection space, event areas and laboratories with sustainability goals targeting the human body, waste, transportation and energy.
- The bio-climactic green canteen and a solar park at the Ellinogermaniki Agogi School Campus that operates as a New European Bauhaus Lab (NEB-Lab)¹³ pilot site to act as a driver of a green neighbourhood living lab.

Sustainability communication with pupils

As environmental problems are reported more and more in the media, it is only normal that adults and children alike are becoming worried and pessimistic about the future of their world. Sobel (1999) has called this “ecophobia”, a fear of environmental deterioration. A survey of children aged 10–12 found that 82% of children expressed fear about environmental problems (Strife, 2015). A larger survey of 10,000 respondents aged 16–25 in 10 countries reveal that 60% of young people are either very or extremely worried (Thompson, 2021). The highest proportion of respondents who are very/extremely worried are from Philippines, India, Brazil and Portugal, countries that have been impacted by climate change and will likely be impacted further in the future.

This fear can turn into cynicism and a disengagement with the problem completely. Fear and despair are connected to inaction according to surveys with adolescents (Stevenson & Peterson, 2015). One reason for ecophobia could be that distant and big ecological problems receive more attention (e.g., melting glaciers); therefore, children become more exposed to problems that they either do not feel like it concerns them or feel powerless against (Sobel, 1999; Strife, 2015). However, there are also findings that show the opposite, and whether fear will lead children to inaction might depend on cultural differences (Szagun & Pavlov, 1995).

¹² <https://visit.kaunas.lt/en/kaunastic/lithuanias-science-island-in-kaunas-to-be-opened-in-2022/>

¹³ <https://sites.google.com/eco2-schools.eu/eco2-schools/the-lab?authuser=0>

Instead of being fearful, students can also be indifferent or lack the knowledge to think of environmental issues as a local problem. When teachers talk in the classroom about endangered large fauna (e.g., gorillas) or destroyed rainforests, students might have more difficulty in connecting these issues to local actions that they can take. In schools, climate change also receives more attention than planting trees, which is an activity that can promote carbon capture and sustain the biodiversity of students' local surroundings. Although it is important to talk about such topics that illustrate how real-world problems are complex and connected to the society and the economy (e.g., intense breeding and grazing of cattle to meet demands), sustainability also depends on the betterment of one's local community and local business. Pupils can learn how the environment has an impact on the local economy, jobs and businesses.

A clear example of the difference between having the knowledge and taking action is given in the PISA 2018 survey that assessed student agency – their capacity to set goals, reflect and act responsibly to effect change concerning sustainable issues (Schleicher, 2021). This concept is rooted in the belief that students need to develop the ability and the will to positively influence their own lives and the world around them. In PISA 2018, 79% of students across the 37 OECD countries said they knew about the topic of climate change and global warming and 78% of students in OECD countries agreed or strongly agreed with the statement that 'looking after the global environment is important to me'. However, only 57% of students thought they could do something about global problems like climate change.

As mentioned earlier, it is difficult to see the impact of our behaviour on the environment. One way to address this is to help pupils understand how fragile nature can be, and how everything in the environment is connected to each other. This connectedness is also a characteristic of how the world's economy and society functions, which can be explored through debates about sustainability.

Pupils can better understand the impact of society on the environment by conducting simple experiments that are relevant to their daily lives. For instance, students can analyse the quantity of microplastics in tap water as well as in bottled water and compare this measure in multiple water brands. After all, if microplastics are everywhere, they may also be found in the water that we drink. Students can also measure the impact of exposing bottled water to direct sunlight to see if the material in a plastic bottle is broken down and released into the water. These two activities illustrate how the use of plastics can have a negative effect on not only nature but also on our health.

Activities can also be more effective if they take pupils' preferences into account. Although hands-on activities can help pupils make a connection with the environment, tree planting

activities by the Life Terra project¹⁴ has shown that not all young people enjoy working in the field and getting their hands dirty planting saplings. Instead, secondary students were more interested in the technological aspect of the activity, for example, the tagging and tracking of trees on the Life Terra app. Similarly, Plantsoon¹⁵ is an organisation that produces QR codes to hang on trees and to provide information on that particular tree. Schools can tag plants and trees in this way to encourage students to keep track of trees over a long timespan.

Finally, as also mentioned in the previous STNS Scientix Observatory paper (Bilgin et al., 2022), research shows how important it is to adopt a positive narrative when addressing environmental issues. Constructive hope, meaning the belief that one can do something to change things positively, is an important predictor for taking action about climate change (Ojala, 2012; Stevenson & Peterson, 2015). Interventions in the classroom do not always have to focus on the catastrophic aspects and the dangers of losing sustainability. While students need to see the long-term consequences of human lifestyle, teachers can emphasise that every person can do something to solve this problem and raise awareness in their community.

Students as evaluators

It is relatively easy to implement self-reported measures such as attitude towards the environment. It is more challenging to use more direct measures of impact such as changes in behaviour, let alone environmental improvements which can only be observed in a more distant future (e.g., air quality in a town).

However, teachers can make data collection and evaluation a part of students' projects. For example, pupils can measure the duration to fill up a waste bin, or the amount of trash picked up from the ground in the schoolyard. Pupils can also monitor the school's water and electricity consumption throughout the year. More systematically, every school year, a new theme can be chosen such as waste generation, electricity consumption, air quality or green areas. Pupils can compare indicators for the beginning and the end of the school year to evaluate the effectiveness of actions taken (e.g., evaluating the impact of a student-led school campaign for recycling and avoiding plastic waste by measuring the volume of waste produced). A new topic could be added each year, without abandoning actions from the previous year. Such school-wide projects can easily involve the wider community, including parents and the

¹⁴ Life Terra is a project aiming to plant 500 million trees in Europe because tree planting is regarded as the most cost-effective nature-based solution to capture carbon. Life Terra seeks to bring people together, planting trees and harnessing and monitoring nature's own carbon capture mechanism and enabling citizens to take urgent action against the climate crisis. They facilitate tree planting, educate future generations, and develop tree monitoring technology. <https://www.lifeterra.eu/en>

¹⁵ <https://plantsoon.com/>

municipality to get support for the project and its assessment. For instance, the municipality can help with setting up air quality meters around the school which pupils can then monitor to determine whether a part of the school is facing a street that has relatively higher rates of carbon monoxide (CO) or dust particles. In a similar vein, the University of Antwerp is running the AIRbezen¹⁶ citizen science project which aims to measure air quality in the municipality by analysing dust particles on the leaves of strawberry plants grown by volunteers.

Students can also be more engaged if the data that they collect can be used by a science centre or researchers for actual research in the field. For example, a project called CHANGE, developed by scientists in a meteorology lab intended to teach students about climate change in a hands-on way, involves students to collect and analyse data (Hallar, McCubbin & Wright, 2011).

The school as a green building

Municipalities and industry can help with actions such as building green spaces and putting photovoltaic panels on school buildings. Students can then do projects around the maintenance of these, and debate about topics such as the sustainability of using panels as an energy source and how to make school gardens sustain life in the surroundings better. For instance, the province of Antwerp supports schools in transforming their concrete schoolyards into green gardens with their “Groene Oases”¹⁷ project. The project engages students, the teaching staff and the parent councils during the greenifying process. The goal is to help schools adapt to a changing climate but also provide an environment where students can learn in nature and not only about nature.

The project COOLSCHOOLS¹⁸ investigates how nature-based solutions can support the creation of climate shelters in schools. Climate shelters can help the whole school, including students, to build knowledge and engage in actions for sustainability.

The Centre for Experiments in Urban Studies (CEUS)¹⁹ in Belgrade is also planning actions like the province of Antwerp by involving teachers in the creation of parks in Belgrade. They

¹⁶ <https://www.uantwerpen.be/nl/projecten/airbezen/over-airbezen/>

¹⁷ Through this website, schools in Flanders can find more information and apply for the “Groen Oases” project:

<https://www.provincieantwerpen.be/aanbod/dlm/groene-oases/kies-je-oase.html>

¹⁸ COOLSCHOOLS is a transdisciplinary applied urban research project that examines the transformative potential of nature-based solutions (NBS) to support the creation of climate shelters in European school environments. <http://coolschools.eu/>

¹⁹ CEUS is a professional association of architects and urban planners devoted to multidisciplinary research, innovation, and development. CEUS aims at enhancing inter-institutional and trans-disciplinary cooperation in an urban environment.

are also integrating urban agriculture as a nature-based solution in school areas in the urban planning of Belgrade.

Developments in the field of sustainability can sometimes be faster than laws and regulations can adapt. For instance, in Flanders there are subsidies for constructions in schools, but these do not consider the need to greenify schools. As sustainability education is also about becoming active citizens, students can also work to raise awareness about the need to adapt laws and regulations to foster sustainability and ecological solutions. Therefore, influencing and steering policy is necessary to incorporate the green transition in the construction process of new schools instead of greenifying schools a few years after opening.

Professional development

How to equip teachers and school leaders to teach about environmental sustainability and sustainable development? As many teachers and school leaders have not been prepared for ESD, Continuing Professional Development (CPD) is essential. School-based CPD, where teachers define their own training needs and CPD happens at the school site, is most effective as it can be in alignment with the whole-institution approach, with development courses and experience exchange. Action research by teachers can lead to an improvement of their current working situations through a reflection on their practices, thus further developing their own competence for handling work situations and contributing to their knowledge level expansion.

School education will play a pivotal role in education for sustainable development and for facing sustainability challenges. Based on their review of existing PD programmes for ESD, Redman, Wiek & Redman (2018, p. 61) suggest the following components for teacher education:

1. Teacher education should address key competences in sustainability and should not define sustainability by the topics that it addresses (such as recycling, the energy crisis, etc.) but ‘by the modes of thinking, knowledge, values and attitudes it embraces’. In other words, knowledge and competences should be linked to action and cultural and social norms.
2. Teacher education should address teacher leadership skills and how to be role-models for their pupils for sustainability.
3. Teacher education for sustainability should target teachers in their early career and in groups to support their development through peer learning.
4. Teacher education should offer an active learning-based programme that provides opportunities to teachers for trying out new practices. A programme that spreads over

a long period of time also provides more chances for trying out classroom practices (Garet et al., 2001).

5. Teacher education for sustainability should include a method for formative assessment, both to evaluate the effectiveness of the programme better and to help teachers reflect on the results of new practices that they try out in the classroom.
6. Teacher education should also target teacher misconceptions as it appears that many teachers tend to think that sustainability is only about environmental issues (Redman, Wiek & Redman, 2018).

CIRO²⁰ and the Terra Mission, and Nature-Based solutions (NBS) MOOCs hosted by the European Schoolnet Academy can help upscaling professional development for teachers' sustainability-related skills. Focusing on renewable energy (emphasising hydrogen technologies) and energy storage systems, CIRO will offer training opportunities for teachers, as well as an educational game, which will be complemented with an educational game app and learning kits to experiment with sustainability. CIRO also organised a competition for schools to develop projects to improve air quality and reduce the impact on climate in their cities. Such competitions help students experience the real application of sustainability topics in an interdisciplinary way. The Terra Mission MOOC²¹ offers ideas on teaching sustainability in the classroom for climate action and provides exemplary learning scenarios developed by Life Terra support teachers. The NBS MOOC²² explores the implementation of NBS in classrooms through the connection with research and NS practitioners, and also offers learning scenarios developed by teachers.

Although the teacher education literature on ESD emphasises the need for developing teacher competences to teach about sustainability, teacher training can end up being too generic if there is too much focus on competences. Teachers need curated content and concrete examples that they can directly try out. MOOCs can also bring such examples to teachers anywhere. These examples should be developed in consideration of the curriculum. New

²⁰ CIRO Project aims to promote the training of teachers and awareness of students, between 14 and 17 years, in the development of knowledge, skills and capabilities on climate change, sustainability, renewable energies, energy storage systems (emphasising on hydrogen technologies) and the final applications of these technologies. <http://www.scientix.eu/web/guest/projects/project-detail?articleId=1067992>

²¹ The Terra Mission MOOC "Teaching Sustainability for Action" - <https://www.europeanschoolnetacademy.eu/courses/course-v1:LifeTerra+SustainabilityForAction+2022/about>

²² The MOOC "Exploring Nature-Based Solutions in Your Classroom" was part of the NBS pilot phase 2 funded by the European Commission DG Research and Innovation. It tested teacher-developed learning scenarios in class - <https://www.europeanschoolnetacademy.eu/courses/course-v1:Scientix+NBS+2021/about>

topics are not always easily adaptable to the curriculum, therefore learning scenarios should have room for creativity for integrating it into the existing topics that teachers need to address.

According to the EC staff working document (2022), school-based CPD, where teachers define their own training needs and CPD happens at the school site, is most effective as it can be in alignment with the whole-institution approach (see also Boeskens et al., 2020). This CPD should not only be for academic but also non-academic staff (European Commission, SWD, 2022). For instance, whole-school development courses and experience exchanges are very popular in Estonia. In Austria, there is an established tradition of action research by teachers which can lead to an improvement of their current working situations through a reflection on their practices, thus further developing their own competence and contributing to their knowledge level (Rauch & Pfaffenwimmer, 2020).

Support from stakeholders

Parents, local businesses, municipalities, science museums and centres, higher education institutions and NGOs can work together to support all the above-mentioned aspects of ESD and promote the uptake of sustainability practices not just by pupils but the whole community. Stakeholders need to take a different approach to the school curriculum and identify the key competences to develop, and also adopt GreenComp as a common framework.

In the EU, renovation and investment support by public authorities can equip schools to provide sustainable, efficient, healthy and resilient learning environments. For instance, the Cyprus Energy Agency in cooperation with the EESD Unit is implementing the 'Promoting Energy efficiency & Developing Innovative Approaches in schools' project through which 25 school buildings in Cyprus will transform into Almost Zero Energy Buildings, by activating public and private investments of €7.5 million. Policymakers can develop policies for curriculum integration and mainstreaming learning for environmental sustainability. Research institutions and their outreach programmes can play an important role in education for environmental sustainability (e.g., Lishawa & Tuchman, 2010). They can also help with in-service and personal development courses for teachers.

There can be programmes to incentivise schools that want to adopt practices to promote sustainability actions in their school and their community. Municipal, regional or national authorities can develop a self-assessment and certification programme for green/sustainable schools. For instance, in Cyprus, the EESD Unit of the Ministry of Education, Culture, Youth and Sports in cooperation with several stakeholders such as the Ministry of Energy, Commerce and Industry, the Ministry of Agriculture, Rural Development and the Environment, and the Cyprus Institute etc. organise actions, competitions and festivals for schools to develop,

implement and present their work around the theme of sustainability. Competitions and certifications can encourage teachers to collaborate more to develop projects or co-teach topics.

Involving parents in projects can also increase the impact of programmes. In Crete, an energy efficiency education programme resulted in students conserving energy at home and sharing information with their parents (Zografakis, Menegaki & Tsagarakis, 2008).

Collaboration with the industry and science centres

Governmental organisations such as the Foundation for Transport²³, or non-governmental organisations can help linking schools to relevant professionals and experts who can visit the schools to talk about topics related to solving problems in a sustainable way.

Schools can arrange time to visit municipal and national centres for environmental research or education. For instance, in the province of Antwerp in Belgium, the Provincial Institute for Environmental Education (PIME)²⁴ offers a range of activities for students of primary and secondary education, as well as student teachers. The institute has also a platform for borrowing fieldwork material. The nature park of the institute is suitable for pupils to study about habitats and landscapes. In addition to an indoor exhibition, the institute has built an outdoor recreational space so that students can make the most of their excursions. They can visit an artificially flooded area or follow a 5 km-long trail with an interactive map using digital devices. For instance, an activity called 'Room for water'²⁵ takes pupils through a riverbank to learn about flood control, the fauna and flora of the wetland, and the plan to prevent the city from flooding. The institute connects their activities and training content to the sustainable development goals endorsed by the United Nations.

Similarly, Cyprus has a national network of environmental education centres located in key areas such as mountains, national parks, lakes, and rivers that offer environmental programmes to all levels of education including early childhood education and care for young children and lifelong learning for adults.

²³ The Foundation for Transport was co-founded by the Malta Chamber of SMEs, Malta Employers' Association, Malta Enterprise, MCAST and Transport Regulator. The Foundation's Mission is to assist industry players to adapt to innovation. <https://fft.mt/>

²⁴ The Provincial Institute for Environmental Education in Antwerp has a website with teaching material and ideas for activities at their venue - <https://www.provincieantwerpen.be/aanbod/dlm/pime.html>

²⁵ <https://www.provincieantwerpen.be/aanbod/dlm/pime/activiteiten-voor-het-secundair-onderwijs/expeditie-ruimte-voor-water.html>

School excursions can be organised in collaboration with the industry or science centres for planting events. These events would be an opportunity to learn about forests, e.g., the formation of new forests, the types of trees that are suitable for specific areas, forest fires, etc.

A database of industries and projects could be useful for teachers who are looking for collaborations for ESD activities. This way, a teacher who is interested in collaborating with the community to engage their students in action could get involved in a project that is already there, or is suggested by industry or the local community, instead of building all activities from scratch. This database would also enable educators to find projects/organisations that focus on specific themes (e.g., CIRO for energy storage, Life Terra for tree planting, etc.). This database would be more effective if it maps the locations of local agents. Schools can then find the nearest local organisation that they can connect with.

Sustainability is an interdisciplinary field with new research taking place every day; therefore, it might be difficult for teachers to follow the latest developments and policies. Companies and science centres could organise short internships or winter-/summer-schools to invite teachers to exchange knowledge with experts and practitioners in the field. For instance, in Lithuania, teachers of any subject have the possibility to work for three or more months in a company to bring back new ideas into the classroom. In turn, experts and practitioners could be incentivised to go for a teaching career or for a temporary teaching job, which would also help meeting the demand of STEM teachers in schools.

Conclusion

The discussions confirmed that stakeholders should view ESD as a topic that can be addressed in all subjects and not as the sole responsibility of science teachers. It is necessary for a whole-school approach, where the entire staff participates in actions for sustainability and ESD is a cross-curricular subject. The examples of what public authorities and schools are already doing, described in this paper, can be an inspiration for all stakeholders in planning their own actions for sustainability.

The discussions also revealed that finding time is a bigger challenge for teachers than a lack of resources to implement ESD. There are many great initiatives and organisations creating materials, but in the end, the responsibility is on the shoulders of teachers who make time and find tools and training opportunities by themselves.

Many challenges were mentioned, mainly the issue of how to reconnect secondary students with nature. Adolescents have the need to be useful and have a purpose, but they might not think that sustainability and ecological issues are the areas where they will meet this need.

Educators also have the challenge to attenuate the ecological anxieties of young people. Personalised activities, for instance by emphasising the use of technology or diversifying possible actions in the community, can enhance the experience and motivate students to go outside and investigate. Participating in STEM competitions and real scientific research can further engage students. The importance of bringing professionals to schools was highlighted as a role modelling practice that engages students and prepares them for choosing STEM careers in NBS and sustainability. The school plays an important role both as a physical location and as a community that builds knowledge and takes action for sustainability. There is room for greenifying more schools and promoting green or eco-school certifications. A whole school policy, and the presence and use of natural green elements, are key factors to successfully involve students. However, more programmes need to be implemented, evaluated, and shared among stakeholders to determine the ideal content and duration of interventions. Finally, partnerships among all stakeholders (industry, research centres, families, schools and society in general) are key for STEM education to effectively address sustainability together with the implementation of the new GreenComp framework.

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